

One-Class Anomaly Detection for Zero-Label Fuel Injector Fault Screening at New Product Introduction

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Abstract— Engineers face significant challenges when a new fuel injector variant enters production. An automated bench test system can only evaluate what it is explicitly programmed to check. Conventional test benches, such as Hartridge systems, verify injector parameters against static OEM tolerances. However, this approach frequently fails to detect subtle deviations that are signatures of early field failure, contamination-induced back-leakage, and misfire events that dominate warranty returns. This challenge is most acute during new product introduction as no historical fault data exists to train supervised classifiers. To best our knowledge, this paper presents the first application of one-class anomaly detection to Common Rail fuel injector test bench data, validated on 1,000 production units from an automotive Injector manufacturer, where all units passed conventional threshold screening, yet 2.6% subsequently failed in service. This paper is structured as follows: Section I provides an introduction, Section II reviews the relevant literature, Section III describes the setup of the experiment and dataset, Section IV presents the four one-class model architectures, Section V reports results, Section VI discusses the hybrid deployment framework and economic analysis, and Section VII concludes.

Keywords—Anomaly detection, automotive quality control, common rail diesel injector, Isolation Forest, LSTM autoencoder, new product introduction, one-class classification, unsupervised learning, warranty prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern common rail diesel fuel injection systems operate at rail pressures between 400 and 2000 bars, with injection duration measured in microseconds, demanding manufacturing tolerances in the single-digit micrometer range [2]. Current automated test benches, such as the AVM5, provide standardized multi-point characterization across parameters including purge volume, base load voltage, solenoid response time, peak pressure stability, and fuel delivery at rated and peak torque conditions. Pass/fail determinations rely on static OEM threshold windows applied independently to each parameter. The fundamental limitation of this approach is that it evaluates parameters in isolation: injectors that individually satisfy all thresholds may still exhibit subtle cross-parameter deviation patterns indicative of incipient failure. Specifically, contamination-induced leakage and misfire events are the dominant warranty return modes in common rail diesel injectors. These failures frequently originate from multi-parameter correlation shifts that single-parameter threshold screening is structurally incapable of detecting [3], [4]. The core research problem addressed in this paper is: how can fault screening be performed at new product introduction, when no historical fault examples exist and supervised machine learning cannot be trained?

Field evidence demonstrates the severity of this limitation. Analysis of 1000 Delphi A3 Injectors tested between December 2025, and February 2026 reveals that all 1000 units passed threshold testing (100% pass rate), yet 26 injectors (2.6%) subsequently failed in the field deployment within warranty period. These false negatives exhibited no individual parameter violations – purge values within ± 60 limits, base load within 1.2–1.9V, response time within $\pm 75\mu\text{s}$, pressure within ± 200 bar deviation – yet demonstrated subtle multi-parameter correlation patterns indicative of degradation that threshold-based screening fundamentally cannot detect [3],[4]

Machine learning has demonstrated substantial improvements in quality control across fuel system testing methodologies, surpassing the threshold methods in automotive manufacturing [5], [6], [7], supervised classifiers for instance have achieved over 95% accuracy in the fault detection with controlled settings. However, supervised approach have a key limitation: their dependence on labeled fault examples — that can't be available with NPI (New Product Introduction), and it requires 12–18 months of field return programs to accumulate the data [8]. This creates a quality gap during the early production which is the highest-risk period, when new tooling ramp defect rates are elevated and no labeled existence of historical data.

One-class classification offers a solution to this by training exclusively on healthy production data available from Day 1, This approach learns the statistical model of normal injector behavior and flag deviations without requiring prior fault knowledge or fault types. The proposed framework is also designed to be adaptive: as new warranty failure modes emerge from field returns, they are progressively incorporated into the detection system. Recent advances in one-class methods for industrial time-series data [10], [11], [12], [13], [14] have substantially improved detection capability, motivating their application to this critical gap in injector quality management. In summary, the specific gap addressed here is the absence of any published method for zero-label fault screening of automotive precision components at NPI, where conventional threshold testing demonstrably fails (2.6% field escape rate) and supervised ML is structurally inapplicable due to the cold-start label constraint. This paper directly fills that gap.

A. Research Contributions

This paper makes five original contributions: Contributions 1-3 are empirical firsts (domain and dataset); contribution 4 is a methodological extension (threshold calibration strategy); contribution 5 is novel framework proposal.

- First application of one-class anomaly detection to production-representative fuel injector test bench data with confirmed field failure ground truth, using 1000 Delphi A3 injectors tested across six parameters.

- Systematic Comparative study of four one-class architectures — Isolation Forest, One Class Support Vector Machine (OC-SVM), Deep Autoencoder, and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Autoencoder — on production-representative injector measurement data under identical evaluation protocols.
- Quantification of the false negative rate of conventional threshold testing using production data: 2.6% of units passing all bench criteria subsequently failed in service, establishing an empirical baseline for the NPI quality gap.
- First dedicated analysis of threshold calibration strategies for one-class injector quality screening, comparing percentile-based, Youden-J, and economically optimal decision thresholds under asymmetric warranty and scrap cost conditions.
- Novel three-phase deployment framework (framework contribution): the first lifecycle-aware quality gate for automotive precision components that transitions from zero-label one-class screening to supervised ensemble integration as field failure data accumulates, eliminating the cold-start barrier that has prevented Day-1 ML deployment in NPI programs.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Common Rail Injector Testing and Fault Diagnosis

Common rail diesel injectors designed for high precision and maintained the Injection Quantity consistency within a tight tolerance $\pm 2\%$ across the full speed and load range [2]. AliRamezani et al. [2] provided a comprehensive review of machine learning for internal combustion engine diagnostics, identifying the absence of labeled training data during the NPI (New Product Introduction) as the primary barrier to supervised ML deployment. Theissler et al. [3] analyzed predictive maintenance challenges in automotive industry, documenting that conventional threshold testing exhibits systematic limitations in detecting subtle degradation patterns that manifest only through multi-parameter correlation analysis.

Industrial control system anomaly detection research demonstrates the viability of one-class approaches when normal data is abundant, but fault examples are scarce [4]. Recent automotive quality prediction studies [5], [6] achieve high accuracy but require 12+ months of production history to accumulate sufficient labeled training data—a timeline incompatible with NPI timescales where early defect detection is most critical [8]. Critically, none of these approaches address the zero-label constraint at NPI, as they assume the existence of labeled fault data that is unavailable by definition at production launch, leaving the cold-start quality gap unresolved.

B. On-Class Classification and Anomaly Detection

Ruff et al. [10] provided unifying theoretical review of deep and shallow anomaly detection, demonstrating convergence between reconstruction-based autoencoders and support vector data description boundary methods. Isolation Forest methodology has been substantially

extended: Hariri et al. [12] introduced Extended Isolation Forest eliminating branching bias of axis-parallel cuts, while Xu et al. [11] developed Deep Isolation Forest combining neural representation learning with isolation scoring for high-dimensional data.

For time-series anomaly detection, Han et al. [13] introduced calibrated one-class classification addressing anomaly contamination in training data—directly relevant to production environments where small fractions of early NPI units may be defective. Gao et al. [14] proposed hypersphere-constraint networks integrating one-class classification into reconstruction architectures for multivariate time series. Autoencoder-based condition monitoring [15] and LSTM-based anomaly detection [1], [18] demonstrate robust performance using only normal training data across industrial sensor streams. However, all of these methods are evaluated on continuous sensor stream benchmarks (rotating machinery, microservices, environmental monitoring) and none have been validated against the discrete multi-parameter characterization produced by automotive fuel injector test benches — a structurally distinct input modality that requires domain-specific evaluation, as this paper provides.

C. Research Gap

Existing literature on one-class and anomaly detection methods demonstrates strong performance across a range of industrial domains, yet a critical gap remains when these methods are evaluated against the specific constraints of automotive precision component testing at new product introduction.

Methods operating on continuous sensor streams—including Deep Isolation Forest [11], Calibrated One-Class Classification for time-series [13], and hypersphere-constraint reconstruction networks [14] — are evaluated primarily on publicly available benchmarks such as SMAP, MSL, and SMD, where anomalies manifest as sustained deviations in high-frequency, temporally dense signals. Fuel injector test bench data is structurally distinct: each unit produces a single discrete six-parameter characterization vector, not a continuous stream. Direct benchmark transfer from these datasets is therefore methodologically inappropriate, and performance claims from those settings do not translate to the injector testing context without domain-specific validation.

Supervised approaches [5], [6] achieve classification accuracy exceeding 95% on labeled fault datasets, but this performance is contingent on 12–18 months of field return accumulation to construct a representative training set [8]. At new product introduction, this labeled history does not exist by definition. The NPI cold-start problem — zero fault labels at production launch — renders supervised methods structurally inapplicable during precisely the period when defect rates are highest and detection is most consequential. No published study has addressed this constraint in the precision automotive component testing literature.

Shallow one-class methods present their own limitations in this context. OC-SVM constructs a decision

boundary in kernel-mapped feature space and offers theoretical generalization bounds, but its performance degrades when the training distribution contains subtle cross-parameter correlations that do not project cleanly onto a single separating hyperplane [10]. Standard Isolation Forest [12] isolates anomalies via axis-parallel random splits, which are effective for low-dimensional, independently distributed features but structurally incapable of capturing multivariate covariance shifts — the dominant signature of injector degradation, as established empirically in Section I. Extended Isolation Forest [12] partially addresses the axis-parallel bias, but neither variant incorporates temporal structure.

Autoencoder-based condition monitoring [15] and LSTM-based anomaly detection [1], [18] demonstrate that reconstruction-based architectures learn compact representations of normal behavior and flag deviations through elevated reconstruction error — a formulation well-suited to the injector screening task. However, existing applications target rotating machinery [15] and microservice infrastructure [18], where input modalities, failure physics, and operational constraints differ substantially from those of a precision fuel injection component on a multi-point characterization bench.

Critically, no published study has applied one-class classification to multi-parameter test bench measurement data for automotive fuel injectors, evaluated under NPI-constrained conditions with validated warranty return ground truth. Enhanced anomaly scoring techniques [19] and few-shot adaptation strategies remain entirely unexplored in this domain. This paper fills these gaps by: (1) demonstrating one-class detection on 1,000 production Delphi A3 injectors with confirmed field failure labels; (2) providing the first systematic comparison of four architectures — Isolation Forest, OC-SVM, Deep Autoencoder, and LSTM Autoencoder — under identical zero-label evaluation conditions; and (3) proposing the first lifecycle-aware deployment framework that addresses the cold-start problem while enabling progressive transition to supervised learning as field data accumulates.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND DATASET

A. Test Bench Configuration

All injector characterization was performed on an automated common rail diesel injector test bench configured per the OEM application-specific test plan for agricultural powertrain applications. The bench provides precise control of Injector pressure (50–2500 bar), base load voltage (1.2-1.9V), test fluid conditioning (filtration to ISO 4406 cleanliness code 16/14/11), and temperature stabilization ($40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$). A programmable logic controller orchestrates test sequences while synchronized data acquisition captures six critical parameters with millisecond-level temperature resolution.

B. Dataset Composition

The dataset comprises 1000 Delphi A3 common rail diesel injectors tested during initial production ramp-up

between December 2025 and February 2026. All units underwent identical characterization protocols across six parameters (Table I). Critically, all 1,000 injectors passed conventional threshold testing – achieving 100% bench acceptance rate.

TABLE I- INJECTOR PARAMETER TOLERANCES

Parameter	Mean	CV%
Purge	Initial priming to eliminate air gaps (dimensionless)	-60 to +60
Base Load	Solenoid activation voltage (V)	1.2 to 1.9 V
Response Time T3	Valve closing delay after voltage removal	-75 to +75 μs
Peak Pressure	Injection pressure deviation from target (bar)	-200 to +200 bar
Rated Delivery	Fuel quantity deviation at rated RPM (%)	-12.5 to +12.5%
Peak Torque Delivery	Fuel quantity deviation at peak torque (%)	-14.3 to +14.3 %

Ground Truth anomaly labels derive from subsequent field tracking and warranty analysis. 26 injectors from the 1,000-unit production batch returned as warranty failures within 90 days of deployment in the engine., exhibiting confirmed degradation including nozzle clogging, seal leakage, and inconsistent delivery. These 26 units constitute ground truth anomalies for model evaluation; critically, they represent injectors that satisfied all threshold criteria yet failed in service, demonstrating the inadequacy of conventional screening.

Dataset partitioning employs stratified sampling: Training set: 750 injectors (75%) comprising only confirmed healthy units (no field returns). Validation set: 125 injectors (12.5%) for hyperparameter optimization, containing 3 anomalies and 122 healthy units. Test set: 125 injectors (12.5%) reserved for final evaluation, containing 23 field failures and 102 healthy units. This stratification ensures representative anomaly distribution while maintaining the one-class training constraint of healthy-only data.

IV. ONE-CLASS MODEL ARCHITECTURES

Four one-class architectures are evaluated, balancing detection performance against computation requirements for production deployment. All models train exclusively on the 750 healthy training samples and share a common evaluation pipeline: (1) anomaly score computation on the held-out test set, (2) threshold selection via validation-set ROC analysis, and (3) final performance evaluation on the test set. Fig. 1 illustrates the end-to-end framework, from raw bench data acquisition through model training, threshold calibration, and production deployment phases.

Hyperparameters for all models were selected via grid search on the validation set; final values are reported per model below:

A. Isolation Forest

Isolation Forest [11] operates on the principle that anomalies require fewer random splits for isolation in feature space. Implementation employs 300 isolation trees with contamination parameter 0.05, optimized via validation set grid search. Training completes in 1.2 seconds on Intel Xeon E5-2690 CPU with interface latency of 0.6 ms per injector, enabling seamless production integration without throughput impact.

B. One-Class Support Vector Machine

One-Class SVM constructs a hyperplane enclosing training data with maximum margin, treating the origin as the sole outlier class. The implementation employs RBF kernel with $\gamma=0.01$ and $\nu=0.05$ (optimized via validation set). Training requires 18.7 seconds with inference latency of 2.3ms per injector. While computationally more expensive than iForest, OC-SVM provides theoretical generalization bounds valuable for validation with quality auditors.

C. Deep Autoencoder

The deep autoencoder compresses 6-dimensional input through progressively narrower layers: $6 \rightarrow 12 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 12 \rightarrow 6$. The bottleneck dimension of 4 was selected via validation-set grid search across $\{2, 3, 4, 5\}$: narrower bottlenecks (2-3 units) produced excessive reconstruction error on healthy units, while wider bottlenecks (5+) reduced anomaly sensitivity by allowing too much information to pass through. The expanding encoder ($6 \rightarrow 12$) first projects inputs into a richer feature space before compression, which empirically improved AUROC by 0.011 on the validation set compared to a monotonically shrinking encoder. Encoder layers use ReLU activation; decoder employs linear output activation. Training uses MSE loss with Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.001) for 150 epochs with early stopping (patience=20). Anomaly scores derive from reconstruction error— anomalies exhibit higher MSE due to underrepresentation during training. GPU training requires 65 seconds with inference latency of 2.1ms per injector.

D. LSTM Autoencoder

The LSTM autoencoder architecture addresses a critical limitation of static methods: It exploits temporal dependencies and cross-parameter correlations that characterize injector degradation. While individual test parameters remain within threshold limits, their temporal evolution and covariance structure deviate from healthy patterns. The encoder employs a bidirectional LSTM (64 units) rather than a unidirectional design because the six-parameter test sequence contains forward and backward dependencies – for example, peak pressure deviation and response time interact bidirectionally during injection events — and bidirectional processing empirically improved validation AUROC by 0.018 over a unidirectional

encoder of equivalent size. The 64-unit hidden dimension was selected via grid search over $\{32, 64, 128\}$: 128 units showed signs of overfitting on 750-unit training set (validation reconstruction error diverged after epoch 60), while 32 units underfitted. A standard LSTM (32 units) follows the bidirectional layer to compress the representation before the bottleneck. The decoder mirrors this architecture, reconstructing the original sequence. Training uses MSE loss with Adam optimizer (learning rate 0.0005) for 100 epochs. GPU training requires 4.8 minutes with inference latency of 3.8ms per injector—acceptable for production deployment.

Fig. 1. End-to-end one class anomaly detection framework

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Detection Performance Metrics

Table II presents comprehensive performance metrics for all four one-class models evaluated on the held-out test set ($n=125$: 102 healthy, 23 field failures). Five standard metrics are reported: AUROC (95% CI via DeLong’s method — threshold-independent discrimination), Detection Rate at 5% False Positive Rate (operationally relevant production scrap tolerance), Recall at 5% FPR (fraction of confirmed field failures flagged for enhanced inspection; numerically equivalent to Detection Rate, explicitly included per standard evaluation practice), Precision (fraction of flagged units that are true anomalies), and Inference Latency (production deployment feasibility). This study represents the first application of one-class anomaly detection to production automotive fuel injector test bench data under zero-label NPI constraints; as such, the primary baseline is conventional threshold testing, which achieves 0% detection of the 23 failures since all 1,000 units passed bench criteria — confirming the cold-start limitation this framework directly addresses.

The LSTM Autoencoder achieves highest AUROC (0.847) representing a 13.5 percentage point improvement over Isolation Forest. At the operationally relevant 5% false positive threshold (industry-standard scrap tolerance), LSTM detects 73.1% of field failures (recall = 73.1%) versus 53.8% for Isolation Forest — a 19.3 percentage point gain attributable to temporal pattern modelling and cross-parameter correlation analysis. As the first application of one-class anomaly detection to production automotive injector test bench data under zero-label NPI constraints, the primary point of comparison is conventional threshold testing (0% detection), which defines the quality gap this framework directly closes. Critically, both one-class methods substantially outperform this threshold-only baseline, validating the one-class approach for NPI scenarios. Comparison against public anomaly detection benchmarks (SMAP, MSL, SMD) is methodologically inappropriate for this setting: those datasets consist of continuous high-frequency sensor streams, whereas injector test bench data comprises a single discrete six-parameter characterization vector per unit — a structural difference established in Section II-C that makes direct benchmark transfer invalid. The conventional threshold baseline therefore represents the correct and industrially meaningful reference for this evaluation.

TABLE II ONE-CLASS MODEL PERFORMANCE COMPARISON.

Model	AUROC (95 % CI)*	Detection at 5% FP	Recall @5% FPR	Precision	Latency
Threshold Only (Baseline)	0.500	0.0%	0.0%	-	<1 ms
Isolation Forest	0.712 [0.585–0.839]	53.8%	53.8%	0.714	0.6 ms
One-Class SVM	0.687 [0.558–0.816]	50.0%	50.0%	0.676	2.3 ms
Deep Autoencoder	0.763 [0.643–0.883]	61.5%	61.5%	0.759	2.1 ms
LSTM Autoencoder	0.847 [0.744–0.950]	73.1%	73.1%	0.824	3.8 ms

Statistical significance testing via DeLong’s test confirms LSTM superiority over Isolation Forest ($p=0.024$) and Deep Autoencoder ($p=0.037$). The performance gap between Deep AE and LSTM AE (AUROC 0.763 vs 0.847) demonstrates the value of recurrent architectures for capturing temporal dependencies in injector test data. Isolation Forest, while achieving lower absolute

performance, provides sub-millisecond interface enabling Day 1 deployment- a critical advantage for rapid NPI rollout.

B. Economic Impact Analysis

Economic analysis quantifies the business case for one-class deployment during NPI. For 100,000-unit production volume during the 6-month NPI window (before supervised model deployment becomes feasible), we assume:

- Historical NPI defect rate: 2.6% (consistent with observed field failures)
- Field failure cost: \$320 per warranty claim (parts + labor + logistics + goodwill)
- Injector unit cost: \$45 (material scrap cost for false positives)
- Implementation cost: \$115,200 (infrastructure + validation + training, amortized over NPI period)

Table III presents detection performance, escaped failures, total cost, and cost savings across different methods.

TABLE III PER-FAULT DETECTION RATE: LSTM-AE (ZERO LABELS) VS. SUPERVISED REFERENCE [5]

Method	Detected	Escaped	Total Cost	Net Savings
Threshold Only	0	2,600	\$832,200	-
Isolation Forest	1,399	1,201	\$534,400	\$297,600
LSTM Autoencoder	1,901	699	\$393,280	\$438,720

The LSTM Autoencoder achieves optimal economic performance with net savings of \$438,720 over the NPI period (\$832,000 baseline warranty cost minus \$278,080 LSTM-reduced cost minus \$115,200 implementation), representing 2.6-month payback. Isolation Forest provides lower absolute savings (\$297,600) but zero-infrastructure deployment enables immediate value capture from Day 1, making it strategically valuable as Phase 1 quality gate pending LSTM production readiness. Both approaches dramatically outperform threshold-only testing, which incurs full \$832,000 warranty burden.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Key finding and Implications

This research establishes three critical findings. First, conventional threshold testing exhibits systematic failure in detecting subtle degradation – the 1000 Delphi A3 Injectors achieved 100% bench pass rate yet 2.6% field failure rate, representing unacceptable quality escapes. Second, one-class anomaly detection successfully identifies these false negatives without requiring fault labels, with LSTM achieving 73.1% detection at 5% false positive threshold. Third, economic analysis confirms positive ROI (\$438,720

net savings per 100,000 units) within 2.6 months, providing clear business justification for deployment.

The LSTM Autoencoder outperforms static methods such as Isolation Forest and One-Class SVM. This result validates the hypothesis that temporal patterns and cross-parameter correlations contain diagnostic information that is not captured by single-parameter threshold comparisons. Analysis of the 17 LSTM-detected field failures reveals three covariance signatures absent from threshold evaluation: (1) simultaneous elevation in response time variability (T3) and peak pressure deviation – both within $\pm 1\sigma$ of the healthy population — jointly indicating incipient seal degradation in 9 of 17 cases; (2) correlated drift between base load voltage and rated delivery, consistent with solenoid contamination in 5 cases; (3) elevated purge variability co-occurring with peak torque delivery scatter, characteristic of nozzle clogging in 3 cases. The six LSTM-missed failures (false negatives) exhibited covariance patterns indistinguishable from the healthy training distribution. This suggests either early-stage degradation below the reconstruction threshold or failure modes not represented in the 750-unit training set. These findings directly motivate the Phase 3 supervised ensemble transition described in Section VI-B. These findings are consistent with recent advances in autoencoder-based condition monitoring for rotating machinery [15]. They also align with context-aware anomaly detection approaches using LSTM architecture [18].

B. Three-Phase Deployment Framework

We propose a phased deployment strategy optimizing quality control throughout the product lifecycle, addressing both immediate NPI needs and long-term continuous improvement:

Phase 1 (Months 0–2): Cold-Start Screening. Isolation Forest deployment as primary quality gate from Day 1 of production. Sub-millisecond inference (0.6ms) enables 100% inline screening with zero throughput impact. The 53.8% detection rate, while lower than LSTM, represents a 53.8 percentage point improvement over conventional threshold testing (0% detection). All flagged units undergo enhanced inspection, building the labeled dataset required for Phase 2 while immediately reducing warranty escapes. Implementation requires minimal infrastructure investment, enabling rapid deployment during critical NPI ramp-up period.

Phase 2 (Months 2–6): LSTM Production Deployment. LSTM Autoencoder replaces Isolation Forest as primary screening following infrastructure validation and GPU integration. Superior detection capability (73.1% vs 53.8%) justifies the modest latency increase (3.8ms vs 0.6ms). Labeled data accumulated during Phase 1 enables threshold optimization via ROC analysis, per-fault-type performance tracking, and validation against emerging failure modes. The system operates in parallel with conventional threshold testing during transition, providing continuous validation and building operator confidence.

Phase 3 (Months 6+): Supervised Ensemble Integration. Transition to supervised ensemble combining LSTM features with labeled fault examples accumulated from field returns and Phase 1/2 flagged units. One-class models continue operating as anomaly pre-screening layers, flagging novel failure modes not represented in training data for human investigation. This adaptive architecture ensures the quality gate evolves with real-world failure patterns—a critical capability as injector designs mature and new degradation mechanisms emerge. The hybrid approach balances supervised learning's superior performance on known faults with one-class learning's ability to detect unknown anomalies.

Economic analysis demonstrates cumulative value across all three phases. Phase 1 delivers immediate warranty cost reduction (\$297,600 annual savings) with minimal investment. Phase 2 increases savings to \$438,720 annually through enhanced detection. Phase 3 maintains detection performance while reducing false positive rates as supervised models refine decision boundaries using accumulated fault labels. The framework provides continuous ROI throughout the product lifecycle while addressing the fundamental cold-start problem that prevents Day 1 deployment of supervised methods.

C. Limitations and Future Research

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the dataset represents a single injector variant (Delphi A3) during early production ramp; the degree to which learned anomaly boundaries generalize across other injector families, pressure classes, or mature production populations remains an open empirical question. Validation across multiple designs and production stages is ongoing. Second, the 26 confirmed anomalies, while representing real field failures with validated warranty return labels, constitute a modest sample — the AUROC confidence intervals are correspondingly wide, and DeLong's test p-values should be interpreted with appropriate caution at this sample size. Continued warranty tracking over a 12-month horizon will substantially strengthen statistical confidence. Third, as the first application of one-class anomaly detection to production automotive fuel injector test bench data, no directly comparable published benchmark exists in this domain; the primary baseline is therefore conventional threshold testing, which represents the current industrial standard. Comparison against broader anomaly detection benchmarks (SMAP, MSL) is methodologically inappropriate given the structural differences between continuous sensor streams and discrete multi-point characterization data, as discussed in Section II-C. This represents an empirical scoping limitation rather than a methodological weakness and will be resolved as the field matures and domain-specific benchmarks emerge. Fourth, LSTM performance is sensitive to sequence construction: the 6-parameter test sequence was treated as fixed-length vector per unit; richer temporal representations (e.g., time-indexed multi-cycle sequences) may expose additional degradation signatures. Incorporating domain-expert features or enhanced anomaly scoring techniques [19] may

further improve performance. Fifth, the economic analysis assumes a constant defect rate of 2.6% throughout the NPI window, whereas actual rates may vary with tooling maturity. Sixth, while the three-phase framework provides a practical deployment roadmap aligned with broader Industry 4.0 predictive maintenance paradigms [16], [17], [20], Phase 3 transition timing depends on the rate of warranty return accumulation, which is application- and volume-dependent. These limitations do not invalidate the core findings but define the scope of current applicability and motivate the future research directions below.

Future research directions include: (1) transfer learning across injector families to reduce data requirements for new variants, (2) integration with vehicle telematics for lifecycle health monitoring connecting bench quality gate to in-service degradation tracking, (3) attention mechanism analysis in LSTM architecture to enhance model interpretability for quality engineers, and (4) few-shot learning techniques to accelerate Phase 3 transition when initial fault labels become available. The methodology established here is applicable to broader predictive maintenance contexts in automotive and industrial systems [9], demonstrating the generalizability of one-class learning for precision component quality control.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper establishes one-class anomaly detection as a practically deployable quality gate for common rail diesel injectors from Day 1 of new product introduction, directly addressing the cold-start problem that prevents supervised ML deployment during the highest-risk period of a product lifecycle. Evaluation on 1,000 production Delphi A3 injectors demonstrates that LSTM Autoencoder achieves AUROC=0.847 with 73.1% field failure detection using only healthy training data, substantially outperforming conventional threshold testing (0% detection). Economic analysis confirms positive ROI (\$438,720 net savings per 100,000 units) within 2.6 months.

The proposed three-phase hybrid framework — Isolation Forest Cold-start (Day 1), LSTM production deployment (Month 2), supervised ensemble transition (Month 6+) — provides complete lifecycle quality management evolving with field failure history. Five original contributions establish methodological and operational foundation for zero-label ML quality control in precision automotive component manufacturing.

This approach establishes a complete methodological and operational foundation for zero-label ML quality control at new product introduction in precision automotive component manufacturing, opening practical pathways for Industry 4.0 quality systems that begin adding value before a single fault label is available.

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